

1 **Geochemical anomalies of critical elements (Be, Co, Hf, Sb, Sc, Ta, V,**
2 **W, Y and REE) in soils of western Andalusia (Spain)**

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10
11 **Abstract**

12
13 A collection of 694 soil samples was taken from 367 sites (at a density of 1 site
14 per 120 km²) in the western of Andalusia (SW Spain) to establish regional geochemical
15 background of emerging critical elements on the <2 mm soil fraction, and provide
16 threshold values for anomaly detection to support mineral exploration in the survey
17 area. The spatial distribution pattern of the soil geochemical anomalies is primarily
18 influenced by the occurrence of magmatic alignments and metallogenic belts in the
19 southern zones of the Iberian Massif. Soils over granitic parent materials are marked by
20 W, Be, Ta and REE anomalies, whereas those derived from mafic igneous rocks contain
21 anomalous concentrations of Sc, Co and V. Most of the threshold exceedances for Hf
22 and Sb appear to be linked to soils on pelitic metasediments. The distribution of Sb and
23 Co outliers is also related to sulfide ore occurrences in the bedrock and could be
24 affected by anthropogenic influences. The Santa Olalla igneous complex, the
25 granodioritic pluton of the Los Pedroches batholith and the magmatic alignment of
26 Villaviciosa de Córdoba-La Coronada may represent exploration opportunities for high-
27 tech elements, mainly for REE, although the identification of promising areas requires
28 further investigation.

29

30 **keywords:** High-tech metals, geochemical baseline, threshold values, anomaly
31 detection, soil exploration geochemistry.

32

33 **1. Introduction**

34

35 There are growing concerns about the long-term security of supplies of raw
36 materials that are crucial to modern technology and society. Variously referred to as
37 critical, strategic or high-tech metals and metalloids, these elements are currently
38 produced in small quantities as by-products, they are increasingly used in a range of
39 high-technology and clean energy applications, and have no effective substitutes
40 (Graedel et al., 2015). The risks of supply shortage and their impacts on the global
41 economy are higher compared with most of the other raw materials, due to the fact that
42 a high share of the worldwide production is only concentrated in a few countries, with
43 China being the leading supplier.

44

45 Criticality is a subjective and dynamic concept. Each country or groups of
46 countries develop their own lists of critical elements and minerals based on their
47 industrial and strategic interests (Hayes and McCullough, 2018). Criticality assessments
48 are subject to change with time and hence that lists are subject to regular update and
49 revision. In September 2017, the European Commission (EU) issued an updated list of
50 critical raw materials with a high supply-risk and a high economic importance for the
51 European Union (European Commission, 2017), which is used to incentivise the
52 production of strategic minerals and metals and facilitate the launching of new mining
53 and recycling activities. Some elements listed by the EC include: Be, Bi, Co, Ga, Ge,

54 Hf, In, Mg, Nb, P, Sb, Sc, Ta, V, W, Y, platinum-group metals (PGM) and rare earth
55 elements (REE). They are increasingly used in the manufacture of mobile phones and
56 computers, LCD screens, electric cars, solar panels, rechargeable batteries, medical
57 devices and many other high-tech applications and products. All these elements are
58 located within the criticality zone (supply risk ≥ 1 and economic importance ≥ 2.8) of
59 Figure 1.

60

61 Most of the critical elements are typically found in low concentrations in
62 primary ore deposits of major metals but they are cycled during chemical weathering,
63 pedogenesis and other surface processes, hence soil and regolith developed on
64 mineralized bedrock areas can be enriched in such elements (Jowit et al., 2017, Négrel
65 et al., 2019). Thus, for instance, clay deposits and clayey soils containing high
66 concentrations of exchangeable REE that are thought to be adsorbed on clay minerals,
67 dominantly kaolinite and halloysite, have become a critical mineral resource in China
68 (Bao and Zhao, 2008). Therefore, the identification of significant geochemical
69 anomalies in soils and weathering crusts is a key issue in mineral exploration of high-
70 tech elements.

71

72 Andalusia is a region in the South of Spain with a long history of mineral
73 exploration and mining, particularly for pyrite and iron oxides, and it is currently a
74 major contributor to world supply of base metals, notably Cu, Pb and Zn. However, the
75 potential for trace elements that are regarded as critical has not been assessed.
76 Andalusia's geology is relatively well endowed with a wide variety of mineral deposit
77 styles and thought to be prospective for a range of commodities (García-Cortés et al.,
78 2011). Its potential for discovering new deposits of strategic metals and metalloids in

79 soil and regolith profiles remains high, but the occurrence, extent and grade of these
80 non-conventional deposits are not well known or not published.

81

82 This paper was intended to improve the knowledge base of critical raw materials
83 resources and their potential in western Andalusia, highlighting areas for future research
84 in geochemical prospecting. The main objectives were: 1) to define the soil geochemical
85 baseline of selected critical elements; 2) to provide threshold values for anomaly
86 detection; and 3) to explain the source and factors influencing the distribution of the
87 major soil geochemical anomalies.

88

89 **2. Regional bedrock geology**

90

91 The survey area encompasses about 45,400 km² of the western provinces of
92 Andalusia, namely Huelva, Sevilla, Cádiz and Córdoba, covering a large part of
93 southwestern Spain (Fig. 2). The most common soils across the study area are
94 Cambisols, Leptosols and Regosols (WRB, 2014). The geology of the area can be
95 delineated into three major zones representing distinct geotectonic environments: 1) the
96 Iberian Massif, widely exposed across the north, consisting mainly of Palaeozoic
97 sedimentary formations that were metamorphosed and deformed during the Variscan
98 orogeny and intruded by granitoids; 2) the Betic Cordillera to the south where the
99 geology is dominated by Mesozoic and Cenozoic sediments deformed by the Alpine
100 tectonics; and 3) the Guadalquivir Basin, an elongated foreland basin developed during
101 the Neogene and Quaternary between the Iberian Massif and the Betic Cordillera.

102

103 The basement terranes outcropping in the study area correspond to three
104 tectonostratigraphic zones of the Iberian Massif (Julivert et al., 1972): Central-Iberian
105 Zone, Ossa-Morena Zone and South-Portuguese Zone, which are the westernmost
106 exposures of the European Variscan Belt. On the other hand, the outcropping rocks of
107 the Betic Cordillera belong to the Subbetic Domain of the External Zone and the flysch
108 units of the Campo de Gibraltar Complex. A comprehensive review of the regional
109 geological setting can be found in Gibbons and Moreno (2002) and Vera (2004). Here
110 are summarized the main lithologic features and the metallogenic framework of the
111 bedrock areas.

112
113 The Central-Iberian Zone (CIZ) is characterized by the occurrence of a long
114 elongated magmatic body known as Los Pedroches batholith (e.g. Donaire et al., 1999),
115 consisting of a granodiorite pluton, a dyke swarm and a suite of monzogranite plutons
116 that intruded into low-grade metamorphic rocks of Late Precambrian to Carboniferous
117 ages. The host rocks belong to an Early Carboniferous sequence composed of
118 alternating slates and greywackes (facies Culm). To the north of the batholith, the
119 Precambrian basement is formed by a thick succession of schists and greywackes, while
120 to the south there is a series of black schists and metagreywackes with intercalations of
121 amphibolites and volcanic-sedimentary rocks. These are, in turn, unconformably
122 overlain by Cambrian carbonatic and siliciclastic sediments. The batholith encloses
123 many hydrothermal vein-type deposits that have been mined in ancient times for a
124 variety of valuable metals like Cu, Pb, Zn, Ag, Sn, W, Sb, Co and Bi (Locutura et al.,
125 1990).

126

127 The Pre-Ordovician rocks of the Ossa-Morena Zone (OMZ) are similar to those
128 described for the south CIZ of the Los Pedroches batholith. The Ordovician-Silurian-
129 Devonian successions consist mainly of slates, sandstones, black shales and quartzites,
130 while the Upper Devonian-Carboniferous syn-orogenic sediments are dominated by
131 turbidites with minor volcanic and conglomeratic intercalations. The complex
132 geological evolution of the OMZ has produced a wide range of mineralization styles
133 (Tornos et al. 2004), including volcanic-hosted massive sulfides (VHMS), sedimentary-
134 exhalative deposits, skarns and replacements, orthomagmatic ore bodies, and a variety
135 of metal-bearing hydrothermal veins.

136

137 The South-Portuguese Zone (SPZ) is the southernmost tectonic segment of the
138 Iberian Massif. The most remarkable feature of the SPZ is the occurrence of several
139 VHMS deposits of world-class importance forming the Iberian Pyrite Belt (IPB). The
140 oldest rocks exposed within the IPB form a terrigenous sedimentary sequence composed
141 of phyllites and quartzites with some limestone lenses at its top of Upper Devonian age,
142 which is overlain by bimodal volcanic rocks within a sedimentary framework. This
143 volcanic-sedimentary complex is covered by turbiditic sediments (flysch deposits) with
144 an Early Carboniferous age, and it is the host for the VHMS deposits and numerous
145 manganese occurrences. About 60 mines have operated during the last century mainly
146 for pyrite, although most orebodies contain appreciable amounts of Cu, Pb and Zn,
147 precious metals and a wide variety of trace elements, such as As, Bi, Cd, Co, Hg, Sn,
148 and Se (e.g. Leistel et al., 1998; Tornos, 2006).

149

150 The External Zone of the Betic Cordillera corresponds to the Mesozoic and
151 Tertiary sedimentary cover of the Iberian Massif. The Subbetic domain of the External

152 Zone forms a complex of thrust nappes comprising Triassic to Middle Miocene
153 sedimentary successions with local volcanic and subvolcanic mafic rocks. In general,
154 the Triassic terrains are composed of red detrital sediments and evaporites, the Jurassic
155 is represented by marine carbonate deposits (dolostones and limestones), and the
156 Cretaceous is characterized by a predominance of marly limestones. The flysch units of the
157 Campo de Gibraltar Complex (CGC) contain a series of tectonic units, mainly turbiditic,
158 and olistostromal formations which range from Cretaceous to Early Miocene.

159
160 Finally, the Neogene infill of the Guadalquivir Basin comprises five overlapping
161 depositional sequences that are progressively younger to the west (Sierro et al., 1996).
162 The basin is filled with autochthonous sediments (calcareenites, bioclastic limestones,
163 clays, silts and sands) that unconformably overlie the Iberian Massif, and allochthonous
164 units consisting of gravity-flow deposits (olistostromes) linked to the southern active
165 margin, as a result of the dismantling and erosion of the overthrust nappes from the
166 Betic Cordillera.

167

168 **3. Soil sampling and methods**

169

170 A total of 694 soil samples were collected from 367 sites unevenly distributed
171 over the study area, with a sampling density of about one site per 120 km². In an attempt
172 to reduce selection bias, the sample locations were chosen using a stratified random
173 sampling strategy based on bedrock geology, as lithology of the parent materials is the
174 main soil-forming factor controlling the soil geochemistry in the area (e.g. Galán et al.,
175 2008). The sites were chosen to represent rural areas with no direct source of pollution
176 other than atmospheric deposition and diffuse contamination from human activities.

177 Sampling was avoided in agricultural ecosystems to prevent contamination from
178 fertilizers.

179

180 Soil core samples were taken with an Edelman auger from a depth of 0-20 cm
181 (367 topsoil samples) at all sites, and from a depth of 20-40 cm (327 subsoil samples) in
182 those locations where the bedrock was encountered at greater depths below the ground
183 surface. In order to improve statistical confidence, the samples were bulked in the field
184 to make a composite sample of about 4 kg per depth interval, at each site, from five soil
185 cores collected in crossing directions and spaced approximately 1.5 m around the
186 central sampling position. The soil samples were dried at ambient air temperature,
187 gently disaggregated with a wooden roller, sieved to pass a 2-mm stainless steel screen
188 and then thoroughly mixed to ensure homogeneity. A subsample of each sieved soil was
189 ground using an agate mortar to recover the less than 63 μm grain-size powder for
190 chemical analysis.

191

192 The samples were analyzed for Be, Co, Hf, Sb, Sc, Ta, V, W, Y and some REE
193 (La, Ce, Nd, Sm, Eu, Tb, Yb and Lu) at Activation Laboratories Ltd. (Ontario, Canada),
194 which is accredited to the ISO/IEC 17025 Quality System. For all the elements, except
195 Be, V and Y, total concentrations were determined by instrumental neutron activation
196 analysis (INAA). A 30 g sample was irradiated at a thermal flux of 7×10^{12} neutrons
197 $\text{cm}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$. After a seven-day decay period, the samples were counted on a high resolution
198 Ge detector. The decay-corrected activities were compared to a calibration obtained by
199 using multiple certified international reference materials. From 10-30% of the samples
200 were rechecked by re-measurement and one standard was run for every 11 samples.
201 Yttrium, V and Be determinations were conducted by inductively coupled plasma-

202 optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES), after a multi-acid digestion (HClO₄-HNO₃-
203 HCl-HF) at 260° C. Quality control of the analytical procedure included the use of a
204 method reagent blank, duplicates and certified reference materials to ensure accuracy
205 and precision of results. The relative deviations of the standard analyses to the reference
206 values were typically below 10%.

207

208 A statistical evaluation of the analytical data, including descriptive statistics,
209 univariate and multivariate correlation analysis, and outlier detection, was applied in
210 this study. In order to reduce bias in the statistical analysis, non-detectable values were
211 replaced by half of the detection limit values. Since the element concentrations showed
212 a wide range of variation, the median value was considered to be representative of the
213 baseline. The upper limit of baseline variation was determined by using the median
214 value plus double median absolute deviation (Me + 2MAD), which is much more robust
215 against the effect of data outliers (Reimann et al., 2005; Reimann and De Caritat, 2017;
216 Vural, 2019). The inter-element relationships were evaluated and quantified by
217 principal component analysis (PCA). The approach used here for outlier detection is
218 based on the upper inner fence or upper whisker in a Tukey boxplot (ISO, 2005). Thus,
219 the upper inner fence (UIF) was calculated as follows:

220

$$221 \text{ UIF} = \text{Q3} + 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$$

222

223 where Q3 is the third quartile (75th percentile) and IQR is the interquartile range
224 (difference between 75th and 25th percentiles). The UIF is usually considered the
225 threshold separating baseline values and mild anomalies (Reimann et al., 2005;
226 Carranza, 2009). All values above the upper outer fence (UOF), which lie more than

227 three times the interquartile above the third quartile ($UOF = Q3 + 3.0 \times IQR$), are
228 referred to as far outliers, and they correspond to extreme anomalies.

229

230 **4. Results and discussion**

231

232 The concentrations of critical elements in soils of the survey area vary greatly
233 spatially from one sampling site to another. A descriptive statistical summary of the
234 results, showing the commonly used measures of central tendency (arithmetic mean,
235 median and mode) and dispersion or variability (standard deviation and range), is given
236 in Table 1. Average content of the critical elements in the upper continental crust and
237 their median concentrations in soils of western Europe (data from the Forum of
238 European Geological Surveys -FOREGS- database) have been also included in Table 1
239 for comparative purposes. The same statistical parameters of the measured
240 concentrations are reported in Table 2, but categorized by geological domains, in order
241 to show the influence of the underlying regional geology on soil geochemical baselines
242 and threshold values for the critical elements under consideration. The upper limit of
243 baseline concentration, defined by the $Me + 2MAD$, are also provided in Table 1 and
244 Table 2.

245

246 Threshold values for mild and extreme anomalies corresponding to inner (UIF)
247 and outer (UOF) fences, respectively, are given in Table 3, as well as the number of
248 anomalous samples detected for each element in topsoil and subsoil. In the case of Be
249 and W, the threshold values separating geochemically anomalous soil samples from
250 baseline were the 95th and 98th percentiles, because their median values were below the
251 lower detection limits. All of the anomalous concentrations were collated to produce

252 anomaly distribution maps of the selected critical elements (Fig. 3). These maps are
253 useful in highlighting areas of potential interest for further exploration, where
254 concentrations exceed the threshold values.

255

256 Several clusters are apparent on the projection of the scores on the first two
257 factors extracted from the PCA, after Varimax rotation (Fig. 4). Together, Factor 1 and
258 Factor 2 accounted for 62.2% (topsoil samples) and 66.9% (subsoil samples) of the
259 variability among the elements, and they have allowed us to establish distinctive
260 pedogeochemical associations in both sampling levels. Factor 1 is characterized by
261 strong positive loadings (greater than 0.8) for REE and Y (REY). The concentrations of
262 REY showed a high degree of positive correlation ($p < 0.05$) among themselves,
263 suggesting similar geochemical behaviour in the soil system. On the other hand, Factor
264 2 revealed two clusters defined by opposite scores: Be-W-Ta-Hf and Co-Sc-V. These
265 geochemical associations are interpreted as formed by critical elements associated to
266 acid and basic igneous rocks, respectively, suggesting lithological discrimination
267 between felsic and mafic sources.

268

269 4.1 Geochemical baseline variation, thresholds and anomalies

270

271 *Rare Earth Elements and Yttrium (REY)*

272

273 As expected, Ce was the most abundant element of the lanthanide group in the
274 soils although its concentration, as well as those of the other REE, varied almost two
275 orders of magnitude among sampling sites. The spatial distribution of REE is similar in
276 the topsoil across the region, as previously noted by Locutura et al. (2012), although

277 there are important differences between light rare earth elements (LREE) and heavy rare
278 earth elements (HREE). Relatively high levels above the baseline concentrations of Ce
279 (107 mg kg^{-1}), La (52.8 mg kg^{-1}), Nd (42 mg kg^{-1}), Sm (8.6 mg kg^{-1}), Eu (1.8 mg kg^{-1}),
280 Yb (4.4 mg kg^{-1}), Lu (0.69 mg kg^{-1}) and Y (23 mg kg^{-1}) were found in Cambisols
281 developed over granitic rocks of the Los Pedroches batholith and in shallow lithic
282 Leptosols that are underlain by metasedimentary rocks of the CIZ, in the Iberian Massif.
283 These levels are well above the median of the REE concentrations in Spanish and
284 worldwide soils (Locutura, 2012; Reimann and De Caritat, 1998).

285

286 Cambisols of the Los Pedroches valley are relatively enriched in HREE (up to
287 11.3 mg kg^{-1} of Yb, 2.6 mg kg^{-1} of Tb and 1.6 mg kg^{-1} of Lu) relative to regional
288 geochemical baseline, suggesting that residual zircon plays a dominant role in
289 accumulating HREE in soil. However, the highest concentrations of LREE (up to 332
290 mg kg^{-1} of Ce, 169 mg kg^{-1} of La, 114 mg kg^{-1} of Nd and 332 mg kg^{-1} of Sm) were
291 measured in soils developed on tonalitic rocks from an intrusive stock emplaced in the
292 OMZ, the so-called Santa Olalla Igneous Complex (Romeo et al., 2006) in Huelva
293 province. The LREE-enriched granitoids are often abundant in apatite, monazite, titanite
294 and allanite formed by magma differentiation (Li et al., 2017). Interestingly, the largest
295 abundances of Eu (13.6 mg kg^{-1}) and Y (103 mg kg^{-1}) occurred in soils on carbonate
296 rocks of the external zone of the Betic Cordillera. When categorized by geological
297 setting, the baseline concentrations of REE in the CIZ were markedly greater than in
298 any of the other zones.

299

300 *Beryllium (Be), tungsten (W), tantalum (Ta) and hafnium (Hf)*

301

302 Total concentrations of Be, W and Ta were below their respective lower
303 detection levels in the vast majority of soil samples because they are relatively scarce
304 trace elements. The content of Be hardly amounted to more than 2 mg kg⁻¹. The largest
305 concentrations of this lightweight metal (up to 10 mg kg⁻¹) were found in Cambisols and
306 Arenosols derived from coarse-grained crystalline rocks of granodioritic composition
307 belonging to the Los Pedroches batholith. In this area, the upper limit of geochemical
308 baseline variation was 6.7 mg kg⁻¹. Some of the most anomalous concentrations of Be
309 may be due to the occurrence of beryl mineralization in granitic pegmatites. An extreme
310 outlier for Be was also detected in Leptosol developed on slates and quartzites of the
311 SPZ, in both levels of sampling, indicating a probable relation with local quartz-vein
312 type Sn-W-As mineralization (Sáez et al., 1989).

313
314 The contents of W measured in soil were generally low to very low, with 85% of
315 the topsoil samples having a concentration below the detection limit (<1 mg kg⁻¹). The
316 soils over the Los Pedroches granodiorite are enriched in W relative to other areas of
317 western Andalusia, reaching levels as high as 113 mg kg⁻¹. The mineralogical sources of
318 the W anomalies are linked to intra- and perigranitic wolframite-bearing hydrothermal
319 quartz veins (Tornos, 2004), associated with late Variscan peraluminous magmatism.
320 An extreme outlier was also recognized on soils developed over mineralized igneous
321 bodies forming the magmatic alignment of Villaviciosa de Córdoba-La Coronada
322 (Pascual and Perez-Lorente, 1987), in Córdoba province. Interestingly, an elevated
323 concentration of W (108 mg kg⁻¹) was detected locally in Leptosols of the Iberian Pyrite
324 Belt, around stratabound scheelite occurrences (Sáez et al., 1988).

325
326 Likewise, the concentrations of Ta measured in topsoil were very low, with 65%

327 of the samples having a concentration of less than 1 mg kg^{-1} , and 57% of the samples
328 being under the lower detection limit of 0.5 mg kg^{-1} . Relatively high levels of Ta (3.9
329 mg kg^{-1}) were observed in soils developed on granite bedrock, where this critical metal
330 may occur in Ta-bearing granitic pegmatites in association with Nb, Li, Be, W and REY
331 (Ercit, 2005).

332

333 The content of Hf in topsoil ranged largely from less than 1 up to 43 mg kg^{-1} ,
334 with the upper limit of baseline variation being 10 mg kg^{-1} in both topsoil and subsoil.
335 Although, soils on Precambrian and Lower Paleozoic metasedimentary rocks of the CIZ
336 had the largest mean concentrations of Hf, the maximum value was measured in sandy
337 soils of the Lower Guadalquivir Basin. The upper outer fence for Hf (28 mg kg^{-1}) was
338 surpassed at three sampling sites. In all cases, the extreme values may have a geogenic
339 origin related to coarse-textured unconsolidated sediments and weakly developed
340 mineral soils (Regosols). Because of Hf and Zr have nearly identical charge and
341 ionic radii, it can be assumed that Hf is mainly locked up in detritic zircon, a common
342 heavy mineral inherited from granitic parent rock in soil.

343

344 *Cobalt (Co), scandium (Sc) and vanadium (V)*

345

346 The median Co content in topsoil was 13 mg kg^{-1} , with a range from 2 to 59 mg
347 kg^{-1} ; the total Sc concentration ranged between 0.2 and 44.9 mg kg^{-1} , with a median
348 value of 10.8 mg kg^{-1} , whereas the total V concentration showed a greater variability,
349 within two orders of magnitude (from less than 2 mg kg^{-1} up to 383 mg kg^{-1}), with a
350 median of 78 mg kg^{-1} . The median concentrations of Co, Sc and V are above the median
351 of the European and Spanish soils (Salminen, 2005; Locutura, 2012). The spatial

352 distribution patterns of these metals are rather similar, as they appear strongly correlated
353 with linear correlation coefficients as high as 0.80-0.91 ($p < 0.05$).

354

355 Relatively high levels of Co (up to 59 mg kg^{-1}), Sc (44.9 mg kg^{-1}) and V (383
356 mg kg^{-1}) were measured in the OMZ, whereas the lowest levels were found in soils of
357 the Guadalquivir Basin. The greatest abundances of Co, Sc and V in soils seem to be
358 related to the occurrence of underlying mafic igneous rocks, mainly basalts, gabros and
359 metabasites derived from basaltic lavas, particularly in the SPZ and OMZ zones. Hence,
360 their spatial distribution appears to be controlled by the parent rock lithology.

361

362 The extreme anomalies of Co, V and Sc in the OMZ occurred at the top of the
363 soils developed on the Acebuches amphibolites, in the Aracena metamorphic belt
364 (Castro et al., 1996). Relatively high concentrations of Co were also found in Leptosols
365 of the SPZ linked to acid volcanic and volcano-sedimentary parent rocks, in which the
366 VHMS deposits of the Iberian Pyrite Belt are hosted. A range of critical elements,
367 including Co may be contained in the base metal mineralization.

368

369 *Antimony (Sb)*

370

371 The total Sb content in topsoil samples varied largely from less than 0.1 mg kg^{-1}
372 to 318 mg kg^{-1} , with a median value markedly low (1 mg kg^{-1}). Baseline concentrations
373 of Sb ranged up to 6.6 mg kg^{-1} in the SPZ and 4.5 mg kg^{-1} in the OMZ, exceeding
374 significantly those of the European soils. There is no apparent association with a
375 specific lithology in the distribution of Sb and it did not show a linear correlation in its
376 spatial distribution with any of the other analyzed elements.

377

378 The contents of Sb in the samples of the SPZ are widely spread from the mean
379 (16.2 ± 51.5 mg kg⁻¹) due to its inhomogeneous distribution in topsoil. The highest Sb
380 concentrations (above 100 mg kg⁻¹) were measured in Leptosols of the Iberian Pyrite
381 Belt, due to naturally occurring Sb-bearing sulfides and sulfosalts in mineralized
382 bedrock. They can be attributed not only to geogenic origin but probably also to diffuse
383 contamination associated with past mining activities. In fact, some mines were
384 historically worked for Sb (Leistel et al., 1998), which may occur as locally dispersed
385 in soil. In the OMZ zone, the greatest abundances of Sb were found in topsoil formed
386 from weathering of carbonate rocks rather than igneous rocks or metasediments. There
387 is a good spatial correspondence between high concentrations of Sb in topsoil and
388 location of the Pb-Zn-Ag metallogenic belts of the OMZ zone (Tornos et al., 2004,
389 Fernández-Caliani et al., 2019).

390

391 Outlier and extreme values for Sb were also detected in peri-urban contaminated
392 soils of Huelva, one of the first industrial cities in Spain (Fernández-Caliani, 2012),
393 where the most obvious cause of the anomalous concentrations is anthropogenic. In
394 addition, an extreme Sb anomaly was identified in the Campo de Gibraltar Complex
395 that is difficult to explain without further investigation.

396

397 4.2 Vertical distribution of critical elements within the soil profile

398

399 Variability of elements concentrations within the soil profile was low.
400 Differences between the median values of the two soil sampling levels were relatively
401 small for most critical elements, as indicated by a ratio topsoil/subsoil from slightly

402 above the unity to 1.15, thus providing a lithological cause for most anomalies as the
403 concerned elements have limited mobility in soil. Exceptionally, Sb (1.25) and Co
404 (1.18) were found in greatest concentrations in topsoil relative to subsoil, most likely
405 due to anthropogenic contributions, although such surface enrichments require a high-
406 density geochemical survey to trace their source. In fact, since some Co-bearing and Sb-
407 bearing ore deposits have been mined historically in the region, it is difficult to evaluate
408 whether anomalies are natural in origin or mining has exacerbated the original mild
409 anomalies.

410

411 The concentrations of critical elements in topsoil and subsoil were positively and
412 strongly correlated, most notably for Sb, Sc, V, Hf and Co. The Pearson's correlation
413 coefficients given in Figure 5 allowed us to evaluate the linear relationships between
414 topsoil and subsoil samples, and then the spatial variability in concentrations of critical
415 elements within the soil profile. Despite most REE are usually immobilized in
416 weathering resistant primary minerals (Galán et al., 2007), such as zircon, monazite,
417 xenotime, some topsoil samples appear to be REE-depleted. This is particularly true for
418 Ce, because Ce(III) can be easily oxidized to Ce(IV) under the oxidizing conditions
419 prevailing in the surface soil, and subsequently retained in subsoil onto clay minerals.

420

421 4.3 Some factors controlling the spatial distribution of anomalies

422

423 In an attempt to visualize the relationships between the abundance and spatial
424 distribution of the measured critical elements and the underlying geology, Figure 6
425 depicts graphically the percentage of anomalous concentrations of critical elements
426 according to the geological setting of the bedrock, lithology of the underlying parent

427 material and soil type. The observed distribution pattern of the mild and extreme
428 anomalies certainly reflects the influence of the local geology on soil geochemistry, and
429 especially the parent rock lithology and the occurrence of ore deposits hosting critical
430 elements in the survey area.

431

432 Based on the available data, it is apparent that the areas of greatest interest for
433 strategic metals in western Andalusia are found within the crystalline terranes of the
434 Iberian Massif (Fig. 6a). The CIZ is the main prospective zone for Be and W, the OMZ
435 contains promising areas for Co, Sc, V, Hf, Ta, and REE exploration, and the geological
436 setting of the SPZ appears favorable for prospecting for Sb and, to a lesser extent, Co, V
437 and Sc. Most of the anomalies of Be, W, Ta and REE are within the weathering crusts
438 of granites and soils developed on margins of granitic intrusive bodies, whereas the
439 most pronounced anomalies of Co, Sc and V were observed in soils derived from basic
440 and ultrabasic rock throughout the terranes of the Iberian Massif. The outlier values of
441 Hf and Sb were mostly found in soils on slates and schists, although a number of
442 threshold exceedances for Hf was also related to sandy soils of the Guadalquivir Basin
443 (Fig. 6b). Finally, the vast majority of geochemical soil anomalies were recorded in
444 Cambisols and Leptosols with little or no profile differentiation (Fig. 6c).

445

446 **5. Conclusions**

447

448 The soil sampling strategy used in this exploratory study has allowed us to
449 determine the geochemical baseline variation of selected critical elements in soil for
450 distinctive geological environments, to provide threshold values for anomaly detection,

451 and to explain the source and factors influencing the distribution of the major soil
452 geochemical anomalies.

453

454 Lithology of the underlying bedrock is inferred as the major source of
455 geochemical anomalies, although abundance and spatial distribution of critical elements
456 not only depends on the parent rock lithology, but also it is connected with local ore
457 deposits and occurrences of a vast range of mineralization styles. Soils over peralkaline
458 felsic igneous intrusions, distributed along tectono-magmatic alignments of the CIZ and
459 ZOM, are clearly marked by W, Be, Ta and REE anomalies, whereas the anomalous
460 concentrations of Sc, Co and V are closely associated with soils developed on mafic
461 igneous rocks of the ZOM and SPZ. The Hf and Sb anomalies seem to be related to
462 soils derived from pelitic metasediments. The distribution of high values of Sb and Co
463 is also related to well-known massive sulfide ore occurrences, notably in the Iberian
464 Pyrite Belt of the SPZ and in the metallogenic belts of the ZOM. Some spurious outliers
465 and extreme values of Sb and Co may have been affected by anthropogenic inputs.

466

467 Prospective areas for REE resources are locally identified in the Santa Olalla
468 Igneous Complex, where there is potential for forming REE deposits including ion-
469 adsorbed type REE mineralization, residual primary and/or secondary REE-bearing
470 minerals in well-developed weathering profiles of tonalite rocks. The granodioritic
471 pluton of the Los Pedroches batholith and the plutonic-volcanic complex of Villaviciosa
472 de Córdoba-La Coronada may also represent interesting prospective targets for high-
473 tech metals, and should be investigated at a more detailed scale.

474

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476

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478 Project “A Survey of Trace Element Concentrations in Soils of Andalusia”, a research
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481

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619

FIGURE AND TABLE CAPTIONS

620

621

622 Figure 1. Economic importance (EI) and supply risk (SR) of critical raw materials for
623 the European Union (modified after European Commission, 2017). Critical raw
624 materials are located within the criticality zone ($SR \geq 1$ and $EI \geq 2.8$) of the graph. The
625 critical elements analyzed in this study are highlighted by red dots. Abbreviations:
626 LREE (Light Rare Earth Elements). HREE (Heavy Rare Earth Elements). PGM
627 (Platinum Group Metals).

628

629 Figure 2. Simplified geological map of the study area and location of the sampling sites.

630

631 Figure 3. Geochemical anomaly maps of critical elements in topsoil samples.

632

633 Figure 4. Plot of the Principal Component Analysis showing variable loadings of the
634 first two factors for critical elements in topsoil samples.

635

636 Figure 5. Bivariate plots showing the relationship between concentrations of critical
637 elements in topsoil and subsoil. Outliers according to Tukey's inner fence criteria are
638 indicated by open circles, and the values beyond the upper outer fence (extreme
639 anomalies) are marked with asterisks.

640

641 Figure 6. Percent distribution of detected outliers by considering: a) geological setting;
642 b) parent rock lithology; and c) soil type (WRB-FAO classification system).

643

644

645

646 Table 1. Descriptive statistical parameters for concentrations of critical elements in soil
647 samples categorized by topsoil and subsoil.

648

649 Table 2. Descriptive statistical parameters of the measured concentrations of critical
650 elements grouped by geological domains.

651

652 Table 3. Threshold values for mild (UIF) and extreme (UOF) anomalies and number of
653 threshold exceedances.

654

655

ACCEPTED MANUSCRIPT

Table 1

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Table 1

Element (mg kg ⁻¹)	Be	Co	Hf	Sb	Sc	Ta	V	W	La	Ce	Nd	Sm	Eu	Tb	Yb	Lu	Y
Lower limit of detection	2	1	1	0.1	0.1	0.5	2	1	0.5	3	5	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.2	0.05	1
Topsoil (0-20 cm)																	
Number of samples	304	367	304	304	304	304	304	304	304	304	304	304	304	304	304	304	304
Mean	<2	14.4	7.9	4.2	12.2	0.8	88.4	1.8	35.7	71.4	28.7	5.9	1.3	0.6	3.1	0.47	17
Median	<2	13	6	1.0	10.8	<0.5	78	<1	31.6	64	26	5.4	1.2	<0.5	2.7	0.43	14
Std. Deviation	<2	9.1	5.7	21.6	7.7	0.7	54.8	9.1	19.4	38.2	14.8	2.8	0.6	0.4	1.6	0.24	10.7
Minimum	<2	2	<1	<0.1	0.2	<0.5	<2	<1	2.1	4	<5	0.3	<0.2	<0.5	<0.2	<0.05	<1
Maximum	10	59	43	318	44.9	3.9	383	113	169	332	114	16.9	5.9	2.6	11.3	1.6	103
Mode	<2	8	5	0.7	8.2	<0.5	76	<1	32.9	107	26	5.1	0.9	<0.5	2.7	0.31	13
Upper background limit*	3	23	10	2.0	19	<0.5	137	<1	52.8	107	42	8.6	1.8	<0.5	4.4	0.69	23
Subsoil (20-40 cm)																	
Number of samples	202	327	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202	202
Mean	<2	13.5	7.6	3.7	11.1	0.7	82.7	1.3	34.5	67.6	27.1	5.6	1.1	0.5	2.9	0.45	16.1
Median	<2	11	6	0.8	9.4	<0.5	72	<1	30.3	59	25	5.1	1.1	<0.5	2.4	0.38	13
Std. Deviation	<2	9.2	5.6	18.7	6.8	0.8	49.1	2.6	19	35.9	14.7	3.1	0.5	0.4	1.8	0.27	11.0
Minimum	<2	1	<1	<0.1	0.4	<0.5	4	<1	1.1	4	<5	0.2	<0.2	<0.5	<0.2	<0.05	<1
Maximum	8	52	34	200	35	4.9	225	19	98.6	194	92	24.8	2.9	3.6	13.9	2.06	87
Mode	<2	9	5	0.7	5.8	<0.5	50	<1	35.6	56	19	4.7	1.1	<0.5	2.3	0.38	6
Upper background limit *	2.3	21	10	1.4	16.6	<0.5	135	<1	48.9	97	39	8.1	1.7	<0.5	4.0	0.62	23
Reference values																	
Upper continental crust ¹	1.9	25	3.7	0.4	14	0.7	138	1.9	31	63	27	4.7	1.0	0.7	1.96	0.31	21
Topsoil ²	<2	7.78	5.55	0.60	8.21	0.76	60.4	<5	23.5	48.2	20.8	3.96	0.77	0.60	1.99	0.30	21
Subsoil ²	<2	8.97	5.30	0.47	9.19	0.75	62.8	<5	25.6	53.7	22.4	4.38	0.84	0.64	2.13	0.31	23

* Median + 2 Median Absolute Deviation

¹ Rudnick and Gao (2004). ² Median concentrations in the FOREGS samples (Salminen, 2005).

Table 2

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Element (mg kg ⁻¹)	Be	Co	Hf	Sb	Sc	Ta	V	W	La	Ce	Nd	Sm	Eu	Tb	Yb	Lu	Y
CENTRAL-IBERIAN ZONE																	
Number of samples	22	26	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22
Mean	4	17.2	12.5	2.1	12.0	1.4	78.3	9.9	53.1	106.3	42.2	8.3	1.7	0.8	4.0	0.62	19.9
Median	3	15	11	1.6	9.7	1.5	60	5	56.7	115	44	9.5	1.9	1.0	4.4	0.74	17
Std. Deviation	2.1	11.1	8.1	1.6	8.7	1.0	60.7	24	19.4	37.9	16.1	3.3	0.7	0.6	2.0	0.29	9.8
Minimum	<2	5	4	0.5	3.2	<0.5	12	<1	14.7	34	14	3.4	0.7	<0.5	0.9	0.15	5
Maximum	10	49	36	6.1	43.2	3.2	247	113	82	160	69	14.2	2.8	1.6	8.7	1.20	37
Upper background limit	6.7	26	21	2.8	16.5	1.5	142	14	106.9	218	80	17.7	3.3	2.5	8.0	1.36	34
OSSA-MORENA ZONE																	
Number of samples	59	67	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	59	59
Mean	2.1	21.3	9.6	3.9	16.9	1.0	118	1.1	45.0	92.8	36.8	7.8	1.7	0.8	4.1	0.63	23.1
Median	2	19	8	2.2	15.1	<0.5	104	<1	44	88	36.5	7.6	1.5	0.9	3.8	0.58	21
Std. Deviation	1.0	11.0	6.5	5.1	8.6	0.9	65.5	1.9	25.3	51.9	18.1	3.0	0.9	0.5	1.7	0.27	9.5
Minimum	<2	2	1	<0.1	0.2	<0.5	2	<1	2.1	4	<5	0.3	<0.2	<0.5	0.1	<0.05	<1
Maximum	5.4	59	30	28.4	44.9	3.9	383	9	169	332	114	16.9	5.9	2.6	11.3	1.60	53
Upper background limit	3.7	31	14	4.5	24.3	<0.5	170	<1	78.3	149	63	12.3	2.4	2.1	6.3	0.94	34
SOUTH-PORTUGUESE ZONE																	
Number of samples	50	53	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50	50
Mean	2	19.5	7.3	16.2	19.2	0.7	125	3.3	39.6	82.0	31.9	6.8	1.36	0.7	3.9	0.59	17.3
Median	2	18	7	2.9	17.8	<0.5	122	<1	42.1	85.5	31.5	6.9	1.4	0.7	3.8	0.55	13.6
Std. Deviation	0.9	9.6	2.8	51.5	7.5	0.7	56.9	15.2	16.6	31.2	12.9	2.2	0.4	0.4	1.2	0.19	11.3
Minimum	<2	2	3	<0.1	7.3	<0.5	16	<1	9.9	21	<5	1.8	0.4	<0.5	2	0.29	5
Maximum	5.7	43	15	318	40.4	3.1	289	108	83.4	154	73	15	2.6	1.8	7.2	1.10	61
Upper background limit	3.7	30	9	6.6	31.8	<0.5	218	<1	69.2	140	53	10.2	1.9	1.5	6.0	0.81	26

Element (mg kg ⁻¹)	Be	Co	Hf	Sb	Sc	Ta	V	W	La	Ce	Nd	Sm	Eu	Tb	Yb	Lu	Y
GUADALQUIVIR BASIN																	
Number of samples	102	139	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102	102
Mean	<2	9.8	7.3	1.4	7.7	0.6	61.3	0.6	27.6	55.1	22.6	4.5	0.9	<0.5	2.3	0.36	13
Median	<2	10	5	0.8	7.9	<0.5	60	<1	27.6	52	22	4.4	1.0	<0.5	2.1	0.33	13
Std. Deviation	0.5	5.1	6.1	2.9	3.7	0.5	29	0.5	11.8	25.5	9.8	2.0	0.4	0.3	1.1	0.18	6.4
Minimum	<2	2	1	0.2	0.9	<0.5	10	<1	5.2	9	<5	0.8	<0.2	<0.5	0.4	0.07	2
Maximum	3.9	30	43	28.7	16.8	2.8	155	4	79.9	150	61	13.6	2.2	1.7	6.5	1.10	39
Upper background limit	2.2	18	9	1.6	15.1	<0.5	110	<1	41.8	85	34	6.9	1.6	<0.5	3.5	0.58	20
EXTERNAL BETIC ZONE																	
Number of samples	40	50	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40
Mean	1.2	13.1	4.6	0.9	9.4	0.4	67	0.7	31	53	24.5	4.9	1.0	0.5	2.4	0.38	19
Median	<2	12	4	0.8	8.6	<0.5	65	<1	27.4	50	23	4.4	0.9	<0.5	2.1	0.34	14
Std. Deviation	0.6	7.2	2.7	0.5	5.3	0.4	35.4	0.5	21.6	25	14.4	2.5	0.6	0.4	1.3	0.20	16.6
Minimum	<2	4	1	0.3	3.1	<0.5	24	<1	13.6	23	10	2.1	0.4	<0.5	0.9	0.14	6
Maximum	3	44	12	2.8	25.3	1.6	191	3	133	156	95	14.9	3.6	1.8	8.1	1.20	103
Upper background limit	2	21	10	1.5	15.6	<0.5	121	<1	43.9	86	35	7.3	1.6	<0.5	3.6	0.59	23
CAMPO DE GIBRALTAR COMPLEX																	
Number of samples	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32	32
Mean	<2	14.4	8.2	0.9	10.4	1.0	93.3	0.7	32.7	67.3	24.5	4.9	1.1	<0.5	2.5	0.37	14
Median	<2	13	8	0.7	10.3	1.0	88	<1	31.9	65	23	4.4	0.9	<0.5	2.5	0.36	14
Std. Deviation	0.6	10.3	3.3	1.4	4.3	0.6	50.3	0.8	9.6	23.6	8.8	1.7	0.4	0.3	0.6	0.09	7.7
Minimum	<2	3	3	0.3	4.2	<0.5	31	<1	17.1	37	11	2.0	0.4	<0.5	1.3	0.22	5
Maximum	3	40	16	8.5	18.2	2.4	219	5	54.3	118	43	8.6	1.8	1.1	3.5	0.51	48
Upper background limit	2.6	29	14	1.5	16.9	1.0	137	<1	43.1	96	37	6.8	1.5	<0.5	3.3	0.52	21

Table 3

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Element (mg kg ⁻¹)	95th Percentile	98th Percentile	Outliers (Q3+1.5IQR)	Number of mild anomalies	Far outliers (Q3+3IQR)	Number of extreme anomalies
TOPSOIL						
Be	4	5	-	12	-	6
Co	32	41	33	14	48	4
Hf	19	26	19	12	28	3
Sb	8.4	24.2	4.7	20	7.1	18
Sc	28.8	34.6	27.9	15	40.4	2
Ta	2.1	2.8	2.6	9	4.1	0
V	193	247	202	11	293	1
W	5.0	8.9	-	12	-	7
La	67.7	80.4	78	6	111	2
Ce	139	154	159	4	227	1
Nd	56	63	64	4	91	2
Sm	11.2	13.5	12.1	9	16.9	0
Eu	2.3	2.9	2.4	12	3.3	3
Tb	1.40	1.69	1.69	6	2.55	1
Yb	5.8	7.2	6.8	8	9.6	1
Lu	0.91	1.17	1.02	9	1.44	1
Y	37	44	34	17	47	4
SUBSOIL						
Be	4.2	6.5	-	6	-	5
Co	32	40	32	16	47	4
Hf	22	24	19	10	28	2
Sb	6.3	16.3	2.9	13	4.2	15
Sc	26.1	31.9	27.3	9	49.9	0
Ta	2.0	3.3	2.4	5	3.7	2
V	175	196	204	3	299	0
W	6.0	9.0	-	7	-	4
La	71.7	90.6	71.1	11	100.3	0
Ce	139	161	143	9	201	0
Nd	56	69	56	10	78	1
Sm	11.3	14.7	11.5	8	16.1	2
Eu	2.1	2.5	2.6	4	3.6	0
Tb	1.40	1.50	1.63	3	2.45	1
Yb	6.2	7.2	6.1	10	8.6	3
Lu	0.97	1.19	0.95	9	1.35	3
Y	40	47	32	10	46	6

Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3
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La

- Extreme anomalies > 111 mg kg⁻¹
- Mild anomalies 78-111 mg kg⁻¹

Ce

- Extreme anomalies > 227 mg kg⁻¹
- Mild anomalies 159-227 mg kg⁻¹

Nd

- Extreme anomalies > 91 mg kg⁻¹
- Mild anomalies 64-91 mg kg⁻¹

Sm

- Extreme anomalies > 16.9 mg kg⁻¹
- Mild anomalies 12.1-16.9 mg kg⁻¹

Eu

- Extreme anomalies > 3.3 mg kg⁻¹
- Mild anomalies 2.4-3.3 mg kg⁻¹

Tb

- Extreme anomalies > 2.55 mg kg⁻¹
- Mild anomalies 1.69-2.55 mg kg⁻¹

Figure 4

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Figure 5

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Figure 6

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

CREDIT AUTHOR STATEMENT

J.C. Fernández-Caliani: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing original draft preparation, Visualization, Formal analysis.

A. Romero: Visualization, Formal analysis, Reviewing and editing.

I. González: Methodology, Reviewing and editing.

E. Galán: Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition.